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Doctor of philosophy in pedagogical sciences, associate professor**PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF AXIOLOGICAL POSITION IN FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10465070>

Abstract: This article widely covers the pedagogical foundations for the development of the value position of future specialists in the process of training future specialists for educational institutions within the framework of teaching history.

Key words: technocratic cosmism, values, kindness, love, care, freedom and humanism.

In our republic, great importance is attached to the development of a system of concrete measures to educate students and youth in the spirit of respect for national and universal history, to improve the organizational and methodological conditions for ensuring consistency and continuity in the teaching of history, and to fundamentally improve the teaching and promotion of history in educational institutions. Many modern Russian scientists (V.I. Andreyev, N.A. Astashov, E.V. Bondarevskaya, I.F. Isayev, S.V. Kulnevich, A.A. Makarenya, V.A. Nechayev, V.A. Slastenin, etc.) by distinguishing the axiological approach as a methodological basis in the training of specialists for educational institutions within the framework of teaching history they think it is possible.

V.I.Andreyev, E.V.Bondarevskaya, V.A.Slastenin and others define the adjectives defining philosophical and methodological principles, or metaprinciples, pedagogy in the research of scientists as follows:

- axiological meta-principle confirming the value-based approach to the study of pedagogical events and processes;
- the cultural meta-principle cultural universal values that include the future teacher in the "field of force";
- a humanistic meta-principle approach to education that denies the technocratic, knowledge-based approach and the humanization and humanization of education, the process of creating conditions for the flourishing and realization of the im-

portant powers of each participant of the pedagogical activity;

The ideas of axiology are representatives of various philosophical schools that have been developed over many years of research. The basis of pedagogical axiology as a science of IN is that the values of education lie in the unique pedagogical interpretation of the most important functions, which implement values in the life of a person and society.

First, according to V. A. Nechayev, value serves as the basis and foundation of any human culture, including culture. pedagogues define its basis as social and individual-personal guidelines, to provide stability to the personality of the teacher and student, to determine the principles of their behavior, to direct interest and needs, to regulate the motivational sphere in the educational system.

Secondly, it is a real transforming force that raises the objective value of a person, makes him a subject of more universal activity. Thus, knowledge considered outside the axiological context becomes impersonal information, loses its educational function, loses moral and spiritual responsibility for the picture it creates, personality peace. This, in turn, destroys a person, deprives him of his perspective, closes and enriches his inner world.

Third, value is a criterion of perfection; it provides the necessary tools for the evaluative and directive aspects of individual functioning, thereby enabling the individual

to live his or her life to the fullest.

The Russian scientist N.A.Kulakovskaya states that the educational component of education sets the following important priorities that apply to teachers and students alike:

- orientation of a person to universal values;
- democracy and tolerance;
- the harmony of cosmism and national ideas; reveal important creative abilities of a person;

In scientific and pedagogical literature, two main principles of axiological analysis of pedagogical values are distinguished:

1) historical-pedagogical (or actually axiological), which includes the identification of the main, established norms and ideas that have been tested and traditionally accepted as the main categories, concepts, principles and laws of the science and practice of pedagogy;

2) innovative, including the identification of effective innovative pedagogical ideas, new values of education and pedagogical activity.

The combination of these two main principles, which is constantly recommended, and the addition of the principle of the excess of valuable material of pedagogical sciences for internal dialectical conflict, serves for students to determine their own attitude to it in the educational process.

Selection and determination of professional and pedagogical values corresponding to the formed level of their spiritual culture, axiological analysis of general pedagogy are important opportunities to show and form that the training of future teachers includes educational work in pedagogy.

Future history determines the teacher's axiological potential, which is the internal, emotionally appropriated regulator of teaching activity and its relation to the world around it.

Pedagogical activity is based on value, its humanistic and humanitarian essence, it is embodied by people and implemented

for people.

The system of universal human values was developed by the scientist N.A. Astashova describes the following:

- socio-cultural values of humanity, altruism, patriotism, nature, culture, art;
- professional and pedagogical values - patience, understanding, citizenship, responsibility, creativity, harmony;
- personal values, kindness, love, care, freedom, uniqueness and beauty.

The supreme goal of the main, unconditional and absolute value of pedagogy is determined by the subject and object of the person, as well as the educational process, and it is the formation of a comprehensive system of humanitarian relations, the basic norms and principles of professional pedagogical activity among future teachers in the process of pedagogical training.

This basic professional-pedagogical value is directly related to the value guidelines of pedagogical deontology - norms, principles and rules of behavior, assessment is the teacher's moral character. By following pedagogical norms and rules by future teachers, moral emotions, empathy, evaluation, mutual understanding and other norms help to form the emotional value system of the spiritual world of the teacher.

In the process of introducing pedagogical dialogue in educational courses in the field of pedagogy, based on the axiological approach, the teacher considers students as an absolute value, caution, respect, care for students, knowing their age and individual characteristics, taking into account their attractiveness is the main principle of pedagogical dialogue. T. Parsons's work entitled "On the Structure of Social Actions" highlights the relationship between the concepts of value and value orientation. That is, the functional needs of society emerge based on the manifestation of striving for standards in social culture

Value orientation also includes the individual's life experiences and dreams. That is why value orientation has its own psycho-

logical description and reflects all the components and whole system of personality structure.

It should be emphasized that the structure of worldview and value direction includes knowledge, perspective, cognition reflecting belief, emotional, behavior, attitude, which unites psyche, feeling, sadness. This commonality in the structure of these realities allows us to use the integrative concept of "axiological worldview".

The axiological worldview is defined as the world view, universal human culture, valuable directions with interrelated essences that reflect their mutual integration, as well as scientifically based ideas about nature, man, society, manifested in the form of ideals, beliefs, behavioral principles and norms according to their attitude. will be.

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J.A.Yuldashev

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BO'LAJAK TARIX O'QITUVCHILARIDA AKSIOLOGIK YONDASHUVNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarix fanlarini o'qitish doirasida ta'lim muassasalari uchun bo'lajak mutaxassislar tayyorlash jarayonida ularni aksiologik pozitsiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari keng yoritilgan.

Kalif so'zlar: Texnokratik kosmizm, qadriyatlar, mehribonlik, sevgi, g'amxo'rlik, erkinlik va gumanizm.

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ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦЕННОСТНОЙ ПОЗИЦИИ У БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ИСТОРИИ

Аннотация: В данной статье широко освещены педагогические основы развития ценностной позиции будущих специалистов в процессе подготовки будущих специалистов для образовательных учреждений в рамках преподавания истории.

Ключевые слова: технократический космизм, ценности, доброта, любовь, забота, свобода и гуманизм.